

The Impacts Of Banditry Activities On Quality Education In Safana Local Government Area, Katsina State

¹Suleiman Iguda Ladan & ²Gide Umar Saleh

¹Department of Basic and Applied Sciences
College of Science and Technology
Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina Katsina State, Nigeria
Corresponding author email: Suleiiguda@hukpoly.edu.ng

²Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, College of Education
Al-Qalam University Katsina, Katsina State Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Organized crimes have been existing in many countries with impacts on the aspects of human life and well-being particularly in developing nations. This article examines the impacts of banditry activities on the quality of primary and secondary school education in one of the most severally affected LGAs by banditry in Katsina State which is Safana LGA. The methods of data collection involved the use of six focus group discussions comprising 07 in number in each group for teachers, parents and staffers of Local Government Department of Education and Social Development This is complemented by secondary sources generated from documentary records of banditry incidences in the LGA as they relate to education in the LGA. Descriptive qualitative analysis was used to analyze the data. The results have shown that the banditry has negatively impacted the quality of primary and secondary school education. This is by way of creating insecurity in schools, creating shortage of teachers, increasing the rate of school drop-outs leads to poor academic performance, kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers, occupying school buildings, closure of schools among others. In order to reduce the impacts of the banditry activities the government has adopted a number of measures, so also do the teachers and parents. More active and decisive measures are needed towards improving the quality of primary and secondary education in Safana and other severely affected LGAs.

Keywords: Impacts, banditry, banditry activities, quality education, Safana LGA

INTRODUCTION

In both developing and developing countries organized crimes have listed and existing up till the present time threatening the security of lives and properties (Vursavas, 2015). According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2024) organized crime is a continuing criminal enterprise that rationally works to profit from illicit activities that are often in great public demand. It's continuing existence is maintained through corruption of public officials and the use of intimidation, threat or force to protect its operations. Organized crime activity varies across countries, regions, crime-types and nature of its organization, operation and sustenance (UNODC, 2024). Examples of organized crimes include armed robbery, banditry, cybercrime counterfeit money making, drug trafficking fire arms trafficking, human trafficking, intellectual property theft, smuggling across international borders e.t.c.

This article focuses on one of the organized crimes listed above which is banditry. Banditry is simply a kind of organized crime perpetrated by outlaws, brigands or marauders who are motivated to steal, rob, loot, extort, or pillage by threat or use of force (Robinson 2000, in Okoli and Ngom, 2024). Banditry is essentially a gang

phenomenon and in the course of their criminal undertakings or operations kill, maims or dehumanizes their victims (Okoli and Ugwu, 2019). Banditry thrives mostly in isolated, rural areas or the countryside where there is the little or no presence of security agents to enforce law and order.

In contemporary period, banditry is mostly prevalent in developing countries due mainly to inadequate presence of security forces in rural areas. In the West African sub-region, banditry is prevalent in several countries such as Chad, Mali, Niger Republic and Nigeria. According to Abdullah (2019) banditry is increasingly becoming one of the major security challenges affecting the West African Sub-region. This is because of the insecurity created by the bandits as they move across boundaries perpetrating criminal activities armed with dangerous weapons leading to the proliferation of Small and Light Weapons (SALW) in the Sub-region.

Banditry in Nigeria is mostly prevalent in the North West Geopolitical zone where it started in 2011 in Zamfara State and then spread to neighboring states such as Kebbi, Sokoto, Katsina, Kaduna and Niger State in the North central zone. One of the foremost organized group of bandits emerged in Zamfara State in 2011 as mercenary militants formed by herding communities to fight in their defense sequel to the vindictive farmland/rangeland conflict between the herders and sedentary crop farmers (ICG, 2021 and Rufa'i 2021). In the North Western states, the bandits have set up camps in abandoned forests and forest reserves from where they emerge riding on for cycles along cattle routes to launch attacks on villages and along rural roads and even highways (Ladan, 2015).

Banditry activities such as robberies, killings, kidnappings, cattle rustling, threats, intimidation, harassment, extortion, illegal fines and tax collection, sporadic shootings to frighten the people have created serious insecurity in the North West Zone. The activities have affected the socio-economic activities of the people such as education. In fact, in the affected states such as Katsina, Kebbi, Kaduna, Sokoto and Niger states, banditry has affected primary, secondary and tertiary education. The recent strategy of the banditry of occupying the Boko Haram insurgents to kidnap large number of pupils and students from primary and secondary schools has negatively affected the quality of education in the North West Zone. According to the United Nations Educational and Scientific cooperation (UNICEF) (2020) the kidnapping incidences and other banditry activities have led to the closure of 11,536 schools in the North West zone from December 2020 to April 2021 which impacted the education of 1.3 million children in the 2020/2021 academic year. The Federal Government has on many occasions called upon to declare "State of Emergency" on the education sector to save it from eminent collapse due to banditry activities in the North West zone (Nasiru, 2021). According to Ojewale (2024) three key reasons have emerged for the targeting of schools and students. They include failure of governance, large forest zones and children's vulnerability.

This article is aimed to examining the impacts of banditry activities on quality education in Government owned schools in Safana LGA. The objectives of the study are to:

- (i) Describe education in primary and secondary schools in Safana LGA
- (ii) Identify and examine the impacts of banditry on quality education in primary and secondary schools in Safana LGA
- (iii) Highlight the response of the Government to the banditry activities in relation to education in Safana LGA.
- (iv) Highlight the response of parents and teachers to the banditry activities in Safana LGA.

Review of Related Works

Some studies were conducted on banditry / insecurity and its effects / impacts on education in Katsina State particularly primary and secondary level education. Umar, Ibrahim and Adamu (2023) investigated the effects of insecurity on student's academic performance in the frontline LGAs of Katsina State. The findings of the study showed that insecurity is detrimental to student's academic performance particularly in the frontline LGAs of the State.

Bello and Suleiman (2023) examined the effects of banditry on women and children education in Funtua LGA of Katsina State. The results indicated that banditry has certainly affected women and children education as husbands/ parents were killed, displaced, girls forced to marry bandits in exchange of their protection. Many

commercial farmers could no longer afford to support their children education because banditry has drained their economy.

Ladan and Abdulfatah (2024) explore the impacts of banditry on government schools in the severely affected Jibia LGA of Katsina State. The results of the study revealed adverse effects on education quality including kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers and closure of schools among others.

Inusa, Orji and Godfrey (2024) assess the impacts of kidnapping and banditry activities on teachers' job performance in Dutsin-ma LGA of Katsina State. The results reveal a significant decline in teachers' motivation, job satisfaction and overall performance due to the prevailing insecurity arising from banditry activities. The fear of banditry activities such as kidnapping has led to increase absenteeism, reduced working hours and lack of commitment to engage in extracurricular activities.

Ahmed, Muhammad and Omache (2024) investigated the impacts of banditry on the education of girls in Katsina State. The findings indicated that banditry has detrimental impacts in terms of installing fear of physical attack, abduction, closure of schools, hinders teachers' ability to teach effectively and disrupts students' ability to learn. It also creates an unconducive environment for teaching and learning leading to decrease enrolment and retention of female students in schools.

From the review of related works it can be observed that Umar, Ibrahim and Adamu (2024) investigation is on the whole eight frontline LGAs and focusing on one of the impacts of banditry activities which is students' performance. Bello and Suleiman (2023) examines the effects of banditry in a non-frontline LGA which is Funtua and examined the effects on two of the vulnerable segment of the population which are women and children.

Ahmed, Muhammad and Omache (2024) investigation is also on Katsina State as a whole and focusing also only on one vulnerable segments of the population which are girls. Ladan and Abdulfatah (2023) explores the impacts of banditry activities on one of the frontline LGA which is Jibia and focusing on the several impacts of banditry on education.

Only the study by Ladan and Abdulfatah (2023) is quiet similar as they focused on the several impacts of banditry activities on education but in a different LGA as this study is on Safana LGA also a frontline LGA. Study on one LGA is more in-depth especially with the use of local examples and banditry incidences.

RESEARCH METHODS

The methods of data collection for the research include the use of Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) involving teachers, parents and staff of the Department of Education and Social Development from Safana Local Government Council. Two groups each for primary and Secondary school teachers consisting of seven participants each were formed. The Secondary school teachers were reached at Katsina the State capital from 1st to 4th July 2024 at a workshop for Secondary School teachers organized by the Ministry of Basic and secondary Education Katsina State. The Primary School teachers were also reached at Katsina, the State capital from September 26th to 27th 2024 at a workshop organized by Katsina State Foundation Katsina. One Focus Group each was formed for the parents and the staffers of the Department of Education and Social Development of the Local Government Council. The questions discussed by the participants are on how would they describe education in the LGA ? , what are the impacts of banditry activities on quality education n the LGA ? , how have they (parents and teachers) responded to the impacts of the banditry activities in the LGA ? Secondary sources of data were collected through desk research from records of banditry incidences, book chapters, journal articles, bachelor's degree project, doctoral degree thesis and internet sourced materials. The data collected from the primary and secondary sources were collected, edited and analyzed through descriptive qualitative analysis in form of the percentages and tabulations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Education in Safana Local Government Area

Majority of the participants (85.00%) of the focus group discussion have described primary and secondary education in the LGA as poor in view of the fact that most rural schools lacked adequate teachers, school structures, infrastructures and instructional materials that are necessary for the provision of quality education..

In addition to this, banditry is prevalent in the LGA for over a decade which has affected education in the LGA.

In fact, Safana LGA is one of the seven front line LGAs that shares boundary with Zamfara state and one of the most affected by banditry activities. The LGA is primarily a rural local government as even the headquarter is basically a rural settlement there is mostly government owned primary and secondary schools in the LGA. . Government owned primary schools in the LGA like in other LGAs are under the State Universal Education Board (SUBEB) while secondary schools are under the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education which headquarters in Katsina, the state capital. The table 1 below shows the secondary schools in the LGA

Table 1: Government and Community owned Secondary schools in Safana Local Government Area

S/n	Name of School	Ownership	Certificate awarded
1.	Government Day secondary School Safana	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary School Certificate
2.	Community Secondary School Safana	Safana Community members	Junior Secondary School Certificate
3.	Government Day Secondary School Gora I	Katsina State Government	Junior Secondary School Certificate
4.	Community Senior Secondary School Runka	Runka Community members	Senior Secondary School Certificate
5.	Runka Junior Day Secondary School Runka	Private individuals	Junior Secondary School Certificate
6.	Government Day Secondary School Babban Duhu	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary School Certificate
7.	Government Day Secondary School Kirtawa	Katsina State Government	Junior Secondary School Certificate
8.	Government Day Secondary School Marina	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary Certificate
9.	Government Day Secondary School Tsaskiya	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary School Certificate
10.	Government Day Secondary School Zakka	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary Certificate
11.	Kais Girls Secondary School, Safana	Katsina State Government	Senior Secondary School Certificate
12.	Government Day Secondary School, Kunamawa	Katsina State Government	Senior and Junior Secondary School Certificates

Sources: SLGEA (2024).

From table 1 above, it can be observed that there are a dozen secondary schools in the LGA. The schools are owned by the State Government, the Community and private individuals. The schools award both Junior and Senior secondary school certificates to the students. Over the years there is a growing demand for secondary school education in the LGA which led to the establishment of schools by the community and private individuals. However, since the beginning of banditry in 2011 to date (2024), the activities of the bandits have impacted education in the LGA. School buildings, facilities and infrastructures are not in good condition particularly in government owned schools. For example, during a visit by the corresponding author to Government Day Secondary Safana on 23rd March 2021, it was observed that some classrooms are in dilapidated condition. Other classrooms have no chairs and desks that students can sit comfortably during lessons. In fact some of the dilapidated classrooms were abandoned and hence were used by the people displaced by banditry activities to sleep inside them.

Furthermore, there is no any tertiary institution in the LGA at present but few years ago the Federal University Dutsinma (FUDMA) have established an outreach center in Safana town which assisted some students of the LGA to further their education to the tertiary level at Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma and the FUDMA.

Impacts of Banditry Activities on Quality Education in Safana Local Government Area

The entire participants (100%) to the focus group are unanimous that the activities of bandits have impacts on quality education in the primary and secondary schools in Safana LGA. This is through the following ways:

1. Creating insecurity in schools: Banditry activities such as invading schools, and riding fast on their motorcycles near school premises have created insecurity in schools. For example on 16th December 2020, bandits invaded Sabon Garin Baure Primary School to kidnap a teacher while teaching his students in the class. In another example, on January 10th 2021 bandits invaded Baure Primary School Baure to rest there, while on their way to the forest. The pupils and teachers had to leave the school as the bandits are armed with guns and other dangerous weapons (Ladan, 2024a). The bandits also move riding on motorcycles near school premises which create fear among pupils, students and teachers. This is particularly the case with schools that are located near the cattle routes used by the bandits. Examples of such schools include Government Day Secondary School (GDSS) Zakka and Nomadic Primary School Runka. The insecurity created by the banditry activities discourages school attendance by pupils, students and teachers of primary and secondary schools.

2. Creating shortage of teachers: The insecurity created by banditry activities has created shortage of teachers to teach the various subjects in the primary and secondary schools. Many teachers employed to teach in primary and secondary schools reject posting to the LGAs affected by banditry such as Safana. In situations where they accept the posting, they insist to be deployed to schools in the Local Government headquarter or large villages that are relatively safe. This situation has created shortage of teachers in schools located away from the headquarter. For example, at GDSS Zakka during 2021/2022 session there are no English teachers for Junior Secondary School (JSS) I – III, Physics teacher for Senior Secondary School (SS) I and Mathematics teacher for JS III. In order to salvage the situation in the school, two mobile policemen deployed to the village volunteered to be teaching English and Physics for the affected classes. At GDSS Babban Duhu in another example, most of the teachers have sought transfer to other schools to avoid any encounter with the bandits who even launched attacks during the day time along rural feeder roads. Most of the teachers that are threatened by banditry activities are those coming from other villages or towns. Teachers who are indigenous to the villages are less threatened and therefore teaching and learning can take place or continue in those schools.

3. Increasing school dropouts: The activities bandits have increased the school drop-out rates in Northern Nigeria as a whole. The North West zone in particular is among the zones with the highest school drop-out rates even before the advent of banditry. In Katsina State, especially in the frontline LGAs such as Safana, pupils and students drop out of school due to fear and or threats arising from the activities of bandits. One of the instances is when parents and or teachers fled to other villages due to incessant attacks from the bandits. According to one of the teachers at GDSS Zakka, eighty percent (80%) of the pupils and students did not seek for transfer to enroll in to another school. Furthermore, in Katsina State there is no existing government policy of immediate transfer of pupils and students from one school to another as a result of displacement (Ladan and Liman, 2021). In another instance, there are parents in some of the most affected villages that withdrew their pupils/students from schools and enroll them into *Tsangaya* schools in neighboring states such as Kano rather than to leave them to be kidnapped or killed by the bandits. It is based on these instances that the study by Lawal and Lawal (2020) found out that Safana education zone had the highest drop out percentage of 46.68% in Katsina State followed by Mani and Katsina zones with 44.72% and 43.71% respectively.

4. Poor Academic Performance: Banditry activities such as attacks on villages where the pupils and students reside and invasion of schools have resulted in poor academic performance. This occurs as a result of lack of regular attendance to schools and the shortage of teachers in some schools subjects. A study by Garba (2022) has revealed that the pass marks to be promoted to the next class for senior secondary is 450 for the nine subjects offered by the student. But the marks were reduced to 350, 250 and 180 marks when banditry intensified. This reduction of the marks was adopted as the students do not come to school five times in a week and there are no teachers in some subjects as highlighted earlier. In fact in both Safana, Batsari and Danmusa LGAs, any day there is an attack by the bandits on a village then the next day or two the pupils and students do not attend school because of their safety (NCC, 2020). The implications are that senior secondary students will not be able to perform well at national certificate examinations organized by National Examination Council

(NECO) and West African Examination Council (WAEC). This in turn means that they will not be to further their studies to tertiary education level.

5. Kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers: Kidnapping of people ransom is one of the major banditry activities in Safana LGA and indeed Katsina State in general. The bandits in particular have been targeting pupils and students for kidnapping especially those in government owned schools as they are seen as government properties that will generate large amount of money as ransom. In turn teachers are targeted as they work for the government and earn salaries on monthly basis. Table 2 below showed the selected incidences of pupils, students and teachers kidnapped in Safana LGA.

Table 2: Selected incidences of pupils, students and teachers kidnapped in Safana LGA from 2018 – 2024

S/N	Date and Location	Pupil, student or teacher kidnapped	Status / condition
1.	July 20 th 2018 along footpath from school to Tsaskiya	Head teacher of Tawanka Primary School, Tawanka village.	Released after one week in captivity and payment of ₦1million ransom
2.	August 5 th 2020 at Danzaki village	Teacher of Danzaki Primary School based on information that he has money	Released after two months in captivity and payment of ₦150,000 ransom with ₦30,000 worth recharge card
3.	December 5 th 2020 at the classroom in Sabon Garin Baure primary school	Teacher at Sabon Garin Baure Primary School who the bandits had grudge on and were kidnapped leaving other teachers free.	Released after one month in captivity and payment of ₦1m ransom and tortured while in captivity
4.	March 2 nd 2021 along a road while returning home from school	Three students of Community Junior Secondary School Gobirawa village	1. Bandits demanded ₦50million as thought the students are government properties. 2. Released after two weeks and payment of ₦1million.
5.	May 26 th 2021 at Gimi village	Runka-based teacher teaching at Gimi Primary School, Gimi.	Released after 46 days in exchange of the wives of Gimi-based bandit leader.
6.	December 13 th 2022 at the school premises during a raid	Female teacher of Sabon Garin Safana Primary School	Released after one month in captivity and payment of ₦2million ransom
7.	February 5 th 2023 at Tashar Bokiti village along Runka – Gora road	Two students returning home after school hours from secondary school	Escaped from captivity the next day to return home
8.	July 7 th 2024 at Runka village	Five pupils and students from primary and secondary schools in the village among twenty four kidnapped	Two students released after one month in captivity and payment of ₦2million. Three still in captivity as at September 2024.

Sources: Maishanu (2021), Ladan (2024a) and Ladan (2024b)

From table 2 it can be observed that there are eight indices that have occurred at home, villages, along foot paths and roads, within school premises and even in the classroom. A total of ten pupils and students were kidnapped including five teachers who collectively spent 188 days in captivity. The total amount paid as ransom is seven million one hundred and fifty thousand Naira (₦7,150,000). This amount is a huge drain to the economy of the parents and teachers which have negatively affect their wellbeing. This besides the ordeal and trauma suffered while in captivity that often leads to hospitalization. Those kidnapped suspend attending

school while in captivity and while undergoing hospitalization. This has affected the quality and of education in the LGA.

6. Occupying school buildings: The prevalence of banditry has led to the occupation of school buildings such as classrooms by the bandits, the security forces or those displaced by the banditry activities. The impacts of the occupation are that it prevents schooling as pupils and students cannot enter their classes. In some situations, few blocks of classrooms will be occupied which still can cause congestion in other classes affecting learning. Several examples are found in Safana LGA which includes Dunkula Primary School at Dunkula village, and Nomadic Primary School Runka and Illela Primary School, Illela. The bandits use the school buildings as resting place to relax with wine, drugs and in certain instances use the schools buildings to keep and or rape the women they kidnap.

The school where security have occupied part of their buildings include Community Secondary School Runka, GDSS Gora and GDSS Zakka. The villages and nearby settlements and there is no government owned buildings besides the schools to accommodate them. Persons displaced by banditry also take shelter in school buildings such as those of GDSS Safana. This occurred as there is no any designated building to serve as camp to those displaced by the banditry activities. In certain instances the bandits even vandalize the school buildings by removing windows, doors and zinc roofing as the case with Nomadic Primary School Runka.

7. Forced closure of schools: Banditry activities such as incessant attacks on some villages have created serious insecurity that has led to the forced closure of some primary and secondary schools in the LGA. For example Dakwarwa Primary School at Dakwarwa village located close to the forest den of bandits was forced to close due to the banditry activities such as kidnapping, theft and or robberies. GDSS Kirtawa was also forced to close due to the presence and movements of bandits around the school as the Kirtawa village is not located along a main road. Illela Primary School was also forced to close following a deadly attack on the residents and in-fighting between the bandits from January 27th – 29th 2022 (Ladan, 2024a). The forced closure of primary and secondary schools is a devastating impact of banditry activities. This is because when the school is forced to close pupils, students and teachers do not attend school therefore no teaching and learning takes place. School buildings are left abandoned with school properties stolen or vandalize. The forced closure of school destabilize the educational system in such a way that the school calendar will no longer operate like in other schools not affected by banditry (Omale, 2022).

8. Impoverishment of parents and teachers: Banditry activities such as cattle rustling, kidnapping for ransom, robberies and looting of local provision food shops have impoverished many parents and teachers. In addition, the bandits deny the villagers who are mostly farmer access to their farmlands and any person that dares go to the farm will end up been kidnapped for ransom or attacked to be wounded. A study by Ladan (2024b) has shown that cattle rustling are one of the manifestations of banditry in Safana LGA. In Mai Lalle village for example, the bandits rustled 480 cows, bulls, goat and sheep during four attacks from June to September 2020. Cattle rustling deny the parents a source of income that they use to send their children to school in terms of purchase of school uniforms, exercise books, textbook, payment of registration and examination fees such as NECO and WAEC. Kidnapping for ransom had the same impact of impoverishing parents and teachers which makes it difficult for them to support their children while attending school. From table 2, it can be observed that the sum of ₦7, 150,000 was paid as ransom. This amount is large enough to make the parents and teachers bankrupt especially in villages where there is low level of income. The end result is that most of the students in SSS will not be able to advance to the tertiary level of education.

9. Halting School Supervision: The Insecurity created by banditry activities such as robbery, kidnapping for ransom, snatching of motorcycles and setting motor vehicles on fire have discourage supervision of primary and secondary schools in Safana LGA. The Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA) based at Dutsinma has halted the deployment of inspectors to secondary schools in Safana LGA. This is attested by one of the teachers of GDSS Zakka who revealed that Inspectors who are in-charge of supervision of the school to ensure quality educational delivery have not visited in six years from 2018 to 2024! This lack of supervision has greatly affected the provision of quality education in many of such schools already be bedeviled by other challenges arising from banditry activities such as chronic shortage of teachers and school drop-outs. This situation is the same with the supervision of primary schools which is the responsibility of the SUBEB. In

instances where the Inspectors visited, they restrict themselves to the Local Government headquarters and visiting schools located in the affected areas requires escort by security forces.

10. Inadequate Teacher Training: Banditry activities are resulted to inadequate teacher training that could have improved the teaching techniques of the teachers towards quality educational delivery. These are in terms of basic teaching methods and techniques, classroom management techniques, learning management system, communication skills, student behavior management among others (PLBC, 2019). In December 2019, the Pleasant Library and Books Club (PLBC) in conjunction with Katsina State Government organized a Teacher Development Training Program for 32,000 Katsina State public school teachers. The training program was conducted in Safana LGA in March 2021. The program was conducted from 9:00am – 5:00pm in local government areas not affected by banditry. But in Safana LGA the period was from 9:00am – 02:00pm. The deduction of three hours was to allow the teacher to safely return to their villages before 05:00pm when banditry activities usually start. The early closure has meant that some modules in the training manual were not taught effectively to the teachers by the facilitators which affect the provision of quality educational delivery in the schools of LGA.

Again, from July 1st – 4th 2024, Katsina state Government under the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education Katsina organized a workshop for secondary school teachers on 21st century teaching methodology at Katsina State Secretariat. Teachers from Safana LGA and other banditry affected LGAs closes by 2:00pm instead of 4:00pm in order to return home early before the start of banditry activities. This is the same case with teachers attending NECO and WAEC marking coordination exercise. The early closure effects their training which has negatively affected the provision of quality education.

Response of the Government to the Banditry Activities in Safana LGA

The Government at Local, State and Federal Government levels has responded towards tackling and reducing the impacts of the banditry activities on quality education in Safana LGA through :

(i) Security forces have been deployed to provide security to settlements in the LGA. They are based at secondary school buildings as mention earlier for example 100 mobile police men are deployed to Zakka village and they are based at GDSS Zakka.

(ii) Following the kidnapping of students from Government Science Secondary School Kankara in Kankara LGA in December 2020, the Katsina State Government has ordered the closure of primary and secondary schools across the State with special instructions to schools in the frontline LGAs like Safana.

(iii) The Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education has directed all schools to form security committees in conjunction with local communities and the Divisional Police Offices. In addition Mobile Policemen have been deployed to schools in volatile areas.

(iv) The Education Secretary (ES) of Safana LGA has conducted an inspection visit to primary schools in Runka, Safana and Zakka on March 21st 2022. The ES has requested teachers whose schools are affected by banditry activities to report for reposting so that so that they can continue to discharge their duties

(v) In September 2023, the ES has deployed some Head Teachers of Primary Schools in village around Runka and Zakka to Primary Schools in the two villages. This is because their safety and security could not be guaranteed by the Local Government Education Authority.

(v) In June 2024, SUBEB Katsina State and UNICEF Nigeria have collaborated to introduce a Community Learning Hub Program on FM radio stations such as Alfijir and Vision in Katsina, the State capital. The radio program teaches children basic subjects thereby providing a learning platform for the children of those displaced by banditry activities.

Response of the Parents and Teachers to the Banditry Activities in Safana LGA

According to the focus groups, parents and teachers have responded in a member of ways towards reducing the impacts of banditry activities on education in the LGA.

(i) Some parents in the affected villages have relocated themselves and their children to Katsina metropolitan, Dutsinma town and to other villages that are comparatively safe and secure. This was the response of some parents following the kidnapping of 24 persons in Runka village on July 7th 2024.

(ii) Parents who have the means usually enroll there children into other schools especially private schools. Other parents who have no means do not enroll there children into other school. Others who relocated to villages without primary schools end up becoming school drop outs.

(iii) Parents have been calling on the State and Federal Governments to tackle the banditry activities that have made many schools unsafe and insecure for learning purposes particularly in the frontline LGAs such as Safana. This call started following the kidnapping incident at GDSSS Kankara in December 2020 and continued up to the present time.

(iv) Teachers who had to travel to village schools where they are posted feel discouraged to attend to their duties regularly on working days due to the banditry activities. They therefore select two or three days in a week to go to such schools and teach.

(v) Teachers who ride motorcycles to travel to their village schools use old motorcycles to avoid snatching by the bandits. Also they do not wear clothes that show wealth or influence to avoid being targeted for kidnapping by the bandits.

(vi) Some Head Teachers and Principals inform other teachers coming from other towns and villages not come to school when there is insecurity created by banditry activities. Such activities include blocking of roads to intercept travelers or an attack is eminent on the village during day time.

(vii) Teachers who ride motorcycles to travel to village schools do not follow a regular route but use different routes to avoid being targeted for kidnapping. This is necessary as teachers in the education sector are not assisted to pay ransom in case they are kidnapped. Only condolence visits by fellow teachers, and school authority and the E.S.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are offered towards reducing the impacts of banditry activities on quality education in Safana LGA.

(i) The most recent security operation at the State level and the other at the North West zonal level code named "Operation Fansar Yamma" should launch major ground and aerial offensives against the bandits in the Rugu forest of Safana LGA. This will reduce the banditry activities towards providing the required security for teaching and learning in primary and secondary schools.

(ii) The security operations should strategize to launch attacks on bandits and their gang members who are living within village communities such as Gimi and Illela villages. This will make the villages safe and secure schools for the resumption of teaching and learning activities.

(iii) MBSE should employ teachers who are residents of villages where the schools are located. This is to allow for teaching and learning to take place and or continue despite the insecurity arising from banditry activities.

(iv) Parents should endeavor to seek for the transfer of their children when they intend to flee out of their villages. The state Government should in turn create policies to ensure immediate transfer of children to other schools so that the children continue their education.

(v) Security agents deployed to various locations in Safana LGA should be directed to prioritize the immediate rescue of pupils, students and teachers that were kidnapped by the bandits before they are taken to the forest den of the bandits. And when already in the forest den of the bandits, a rescue operation should be organized to ensure the safe rescue of those kidnapped.

(vi) SUBEB and MBSE should conduct a head count and assessment of the schools vandalized by the bandits with a view of renovating them for the resumption of teaching and learning in a conducive environment. Bandits who have taken over primary and secondary schools or are using them for their relaxation should be flushed out.

(vii) Katsina State Government through the office of Special Adviser on victims of banditry activities should continue to assist parents and teachers that were impoverished by banditry. In addition, the Adolescent Girls Initiative for Learning and Empowerment (AGILE) project and UNICEF should be contacted to also assist pupils, students and teachers who become victims of kidnapping to enable them resume learning and teaching activities.

CONCLUSION

The banditry activities that began in 2011 had affected quality educational delivery in the North West zone of Nigeria. This article focuses on one of the State of the zone which is Katsina State and then Safana LGA as one of the frontline areas affected by the activities. The banditry activities that started since 2011 have affected

the segments of the society including education. This article argues that banditry activities have negatively affected the quality of primary and secondary school education in Safana LGA. This is by way of creating insecurity in schools, engaging in criminal activities that affected pupils, students, teachers and parents and even leading to closure of schools. Parents and teachers have responded towards reducing the impacts and or to save themselves from the bandits but the responses are not enough to guarantee the provision of quality education in the LGA. Therefore Government at local, State and Federal levels including relevant stakeholders should take decisive actions against banditry activities to restore the quality of primary and secondary school education in the LGA.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, A. (2019). Rural Banditry, Regional Security and Integration in West Africa. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* 2(3) 654 – 664
- Ahmed, A.S., Muhammad, M.B. and Omache, C.O. (2024). Impacts of Banditry on Girl – Child Education in Conflict Affected Regions: A Case Study of Katsina State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Development Studies*. 2(1) 11-20.
- Bello, T. and Suleiman, M.R. (2023). Effects of Banditry on Women and Children Education in Nigeria: A Study of Funtua Local Government Area of Katsina State 2018 – 2022. *Zamfara Journal of Politics and Development* 4(1) 328 – 384.
- Charanchi, I.M., Muhammad, T. and Faru, A.M.(2023) A Study of the Effects of Pervasive Teaching and Learning Conditions in the Midst of Insecurity: A Case Study of Some Selected Affected Areas in Katsina State *International Journal of Inclusive and Sustainable Education* 2(7) 38 – 47.
- Garba, B. (2022). Effects of Banditry on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Katsina State: A Case Study of Safana Local Government Area BSc. Ed. Mathematics Project Submitted to the Department of Education Umaru Musa Yar’adua University Katsina.
- Inusa, B.A., Orji, R.C. and Godfrey, G.S. (2024). Influence of Kidnapping and Banditry Activities on Teachers’ Job Performance in Dutsin-ma Local Government Area, Katsina State Nigeria. *Sapientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Development Studies* 7(2) 243 – 252.
- Ladan, S. I. (2024a). List of Banditry Incidences in Katsina State from September 2019 to September 2024. A. Private Collection of Banditry Incidences in Katsina State.
- Ladan, S. I. and Liman, S. (2021). Factors Responsible for the Creation of Internally Displaced Persons and the Challenges they are facing in Katsina State. *Journal of Conflict Resolution and Social Issues* 2(1). 11-24
- Ladan, S.I. (2024b). Manifestation of Banditry in Safana Area of Katsina State North Western Nigeria: A.C Okoli and S.Ngom *Banditry and Security Crisis in Nigeria* Chapter 8 Routledge Studies in Peace, Conflict Security in Africa London. Chapter 8.
- Ladan, S.I. and Abdulfatah, A.T. (2023). Impacts of Banditry Activities on Quality Education: An Overview of Government Schools in Jibia Local Government Area of Katsina State. *Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE)* 3(6) 259 – 269.
- Lawal, N. and Lawal, B. (2020) An Assessment of Primary School Pupils Enrolment and Drop Out Rates in Katsina State. *Journal of The Nigerian Council of Educational Psychologists* 12(1) 307 – 319.
- Maishanu, A. A. (2021) – Exclusive: Notorious Bandit Sets Condition for Peace in Katsina State. <https://www.premium.com/news/headlines/481699-exclusive>
- Mustapha, T. (2022). Katsina State, UNICEF Support Out – of – School Children. <https://von.gov.katsina-state-unicef-support-out-of-school-children>
- Okoli, A.C. and Ngom, S. (2024) Situating Banditry and Security Crisis in Nigeria In: A.C. and S. Ngom (eds) *Banditry and Security Crisis in Nigeria*. Routledge Studies in Peace, Conflict and Security in Africa London Chapter 1.
- Okoli, A.C. and Ugwu, A.C. (2019) Of Marauders and Brigands: Scoping the Threat of Rural Banditry in Nigeria’s North West. *Brazilian Journal of African Studies* 4(8) 201 – 222
- Omale, Z. (2022). Katsina Students Urge Governments to Secure Schools Against Bandits and Protect Children. <https://ait.live/katsina-students->

- Safana Local Government Education Authority (SLGEA) (2024). List of Secondary Schools in Safana Local Government Area. A Document Produced by the SLGEA.
- Umar, M.K., Ibrahim, U.K. and Adamu, I. (2023) Effects of Insecurity on Students Academic Performance in Katsina State Schools – A Case Study of the Frontline Local Government Areas *Modern Journal of Social of Science and Humanities*. 18. 1 – 9.
- United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime (UNODC) E4J University Module Series: Organized Crime <https://www.unodc.org/>
- Vursavas, F, (2015). The Problems Faced Fighting Organized Crime Globally and the Role and Effectiveness of Law Enforcement Training: The TADOC Case Study. Ph.D. Thesis Submitted to Graduate School Network Rangers University of New Jersey, USA